

6G SNS

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Welcome to the MULTIX Newsletter!

Welcome to the first edition of the MultiX newsletter, covering our foundational first six months (January–June 2025)! Inside, we introduce our core vision for 6G Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) perceptive networks, recap our global outreach at major industry events like MWC and EuCNC 2025, and introduce the 17-partner consortium driving this innovation alongside our very first project deliverables.

MultiX Newsletter #1: Shaping the Future of 6G Perceptive Networks

Period: January 2025 – June 2025 (Months 1-6)

Launched in January 2025, the MultiX-6G Project brings together a consortium of 17 partners from 7 European countries. Over the past six months, we have laid the groundwork to revolutionize next-generation connectivity by turning networks into intelligent systems capable of perceiving and interacting with their environment through Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC).

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Our Vision: The 6G Perceptive Network

MultiX aims to revolutionize the 3GPP Radio Access Network (RAN) design by developing a pioneering **MultiX fusion Perceptive 6G-RAN system (MP6R)**. By integrating multi-sensor, multi-band, multi-static, and multi-technology capabilities, we are turning networks into intelligent systems capable of perceiving and interacting with their environment through ISAC.

Our architecture is built on three core innovation pillars:

- **MultiX Perception System (MPS):** Embedding sensing directly into the RAN stack for plug & play ISAC.
- **MP6R Controller (MP6RC):** Coordinating multi-technology integration, including radar, LiDAR, and cameras.
- **Data Access and Security Hub (DASH):** Ensuring secure, distributed, and privacy-preserving data handling.

Driving Real-World Impact: Our Key Use Cases

To validate these innovations and accelerate 6G adoption, MultiX is currently developing two TRL 4-5 Proofs-of-Concept (PoCs):

- **Multi-layer Network Digital Twin for Industrial Manufacturing:** By integrating radar, LiDAR, and AI-driven analytics, this PoC enables real-time sensing and digital twinning

of industrial processes. It enhances predictive maintenance, safety monitoring, and process optimization. Robots and autonomous vehicles benefit from ultra-precise localization and navigation, and the PoC explores adaptive network slicing to support latency-sensitive control loops in Industry 4.0.

- **Contact-free eHealth Monitoring at Home Environment:** This PoC enables privacy-preserving, real-time health monitoring using RF, vision, and bio-signal sensors to track vital signs, posture, and detect potentially critical circumstances (for instance falls). It integrates edge AI for the continuous assessment of physiological conditions—improving elderly and chronic disease patient care—while ensuring secure, encrypted health data transmission that complies with regulatory requirements.

Beyond these PoCs, the MultiX architecture is designed to support autonomous systems, urban mobility, smart cities, and mission-critical applications such as search and rescue operations.

Meet the MultiX Consortium

A project of this ambition requires the best minds in Europe. Over the last months, we have been proudly introducing our partners on social media. Here is how our diverse consortium is making 6G ISAC a reality:

Coordination & Technical Leadership:

UC3M (Coordinator): Driving the overall project, transforming 6G networks by integrating multi-sensor perception and exploring passive sensing in IEEE 802.11.

NEC Laboratories Europe (Technical Manager): Driving the project technical vision, leading the design of the MultiX architecture (WP2), and developing low-power AI algorithms for distributed multi-static networks.

Telecom Operators:

Telefónica: Leveraging its unique operator expertise to lead WP1 (Use cases and reference scenarios) and defining the KPIs associated with the different 6G scenarios.

OTE Group: Contributing to use cases and KPIs, driving the techno-economic evaluation, and providing its 5G/Cloud testbed and IoT smart home solution for the project demonstrations.

Industry Innovators & SMEs:

Intel (Innovation Manager): Leading WP5, creating the Wi-Fi network Digital Twin for our PoCs, and integrating active Wi-Fi sensing and multi-modal vision models.

Siemens AG: Providing industrial manufacturing use cases, focusing on radio resource allocation based on QoS profiles, and leading the Digital Twin Proof of Concept (PoC #1).

InterDigital: Contributing foundational wireless and AI technologies, and driving 6G standards and industry forums.

Nextworks: Bringing expertise in system-level design, implementing the DASH component for sensing data fusion and exposure, and coordinating the integration of our PoCs (WP4).

BubbleRAN: Investigating RAN optimization based on ISAC and Generative AI, and developing an intelligence xApp to demonstrate the benefits of sensing on RAN performance.

Apple: Defining use cases and evaluating KPIs/KVIs. Leading the secure data integration for the DASH platform and actively driving 6G standardization efforts in IEEE 802.11, 3GPP, and ETSI.

Leading Research Centers & Universities:

CNIT (Polito & UniPD): Leading WP3 (MultiX Perception System), building multi-band PHY layer enablers, and investigating low-power AI methods to enhance perception accuracy.

KU Leuven: Leading the "Perception Enablers" task, developing channel models and ISAC waveforms, and spearheading the eHealth Monitoring Proof of Concept (PoC#2).

i2CAT: Integrating multi-sensor fusion (5G-NR, GPS, LiDAR) into the 6G-RAN architecture, applying advanced AI for sensor fusion, and leading dissemination activities.

IMDEA Networks Institute: Leading the "Multi-technology, Multi-static Sensing Integration" task and developing the IMDEA mmWave multi-band node for practical evaluation.

Universidad de Cantabria, UC (Open Science Manager): Leading the development of multi-sensor fusion, sensor selection, and new connection paradigms, as well as managing Open Science practices.

IASA: Leading activities on techno-economic, environmental, and societal analysis to provide deployment guidelines for operators.

IHP: Investigating waveforms and channel models for ISAC, developing multi-band algorithms, and providing multi-functional wireless hardware testbeds (Sub-6, mmWave).

Project Kick-Off and First Plenary

We officially launched the project with our Kick-Off Meeting in January 2025, hosted by our coordinator, **Universidad Carlos III de Madrid (UC3M)** in Spain. Here, we set our milestones, kicked off the Work Packages, and aligned our technical vision and collaborations.

In May 2025, the consortium gathered again for a highly productive plenary meeting hosted by **Intel** in Munich, Germany. Over three days, we shared key technical milestones, sparked cross-disciplinary collaboration, and aligned our future directions for 6G intelligence and sensing.

Global Outreach: MWC & EuCNC 2025

MultiX has been highly active in sharing our vision across the globe during this first semester:

- Mobile World Congress (MWC) 2025 (Barcelona, Spain):** We had a fantastic showcase at MWC! Our partner **InterDigital** presented a live demonstration of how ISAC can be used in cellular networks. Led by Sebastian Robitzsch, the demo proved that our vision for intelligent and perceptive networks is already becoming a tangible reality. You can see our presence on our Youtube channel [MWC 2025 playlist](#).
- EuCNC & 6G Summit 2025 (Poznań, Poland):** MultiX had a significant presence at this leading European telecom summit in June. We welcomed numerous visitors—including representatives from the European Commission—at our **Booth**, where our coordinator Antonio De La Oliva showcased our MP6R architecture. We also actively shaped the 6G conversation by organizing a Workshop dedicated to the European ISAC Research Framework and presenting our vision across three different Special Sessions, covering 6G architecture blueprints, sensing approaches, and strategies to accelerate EU research into global standards. You can watch our demo [here](#)!

✓ **Workshop 10: Integrated Sensing & Communications (ISAC) – European Research Framework**, June 3, 14:00 - 17:30

✍ **Special Session 2: 6G Architecture Blueprint and Key Innovations: A European Perspective**, June 4, 11:00 - 12:30

✍ **Special Session 6: Integrated Sensing and Communications Towards 6G**, June 4, 16:00 - 17:30

✍ **Special Session 11: How to accelerate EU Funded Research results via Global Standards Activities** June 5, 16:00 - 17:30

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June 3-6

- SNS JU Webinars:** In February, our coordinator presented the MP6R architecture at the SNS JU Call 3 Projects Introduction Webinars, detailing our MPS, MP6R Controller, and the DASH. You can watch it now [here!](#)
- Global Science Platforms:** Our mission was featured globally in multiple languages on leading science platforms, including *EurekaAlert!* and *AlphaGalileo*, as well as in *The Innovation Platform* magazine.

Key Milestones and Deliverables

During this initial phase, we have successfully achieved **Milestone 2 (MS2)** by completing the initial analysis of use cases and requirements.

We have also released our first foundational deliverables:

- D5.1 - Data Management Plan:** Detailing our strong commitment to Open Science and FAIR principles to ensure our datasets and algorithms are accessible to the research community.
- D5.2 - Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Strategy Plan (CoDESP):** Outlining our strategy to maximize our impact on 6G ecosystems and standardization bodies.

You can access our public deliverables, resources, and open-source materials through our official website and our [Zenodo Community](#).

Stay Connected!

Don't miss any updates on our journey to redefine 6G. Follow us on your preferred platform:

- **Website:** <https://multix-6g.eu/>
- **LinkedIn:** [MultiX-6G](#)
- **X (Twitter):** [@MultiX6GProject](#)
- **Mastodon:** [@MultiX6GProject](#)
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